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pH-Metric Studies on the Copper Benzamidothiosemicarbazide Complex

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INTERACTION between thiosemicarbazide, $\text{NH}_2\text{C}(\text{X})\text{NHNH}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{O}, \text{S}, \text{Se}$) and $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ has been reported by Ajayi *et al*¹ and stability constants were calculated by polarographic method. Stability constant and heat of formation of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complex of thiosemicarbazide were determined by Goddard and coworkers². Campbell and Grzeskowiak³ prepared two series of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes of thiosemicarbazide and elucidated their structure employing ultraviolet and visible spectroscopic technique. In our earlier communication⁴, extensive studies on the interaction of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ with benzamidothiosemicarbazide in solution and in solid state were reported.

In the present communication, pH-metric results of our studies on the composition as well as the stepwise stability constant and overall stability constant of benzamidothiosemicarbazide (abbreviated as BTSC) complex of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ have been reported.

Experimental

Benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) was prepared by the method described by Verma⁵ and its solution was prepared by dissolving weighed amounts in 80 : 20 ethyl alcohol : water mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solution of copper acetate was prepared by dissolving the salt (B. D. H., 'AR' grade) in doubly distilled CO_2 free water. The strength of the solution was determined by the usual method. Fresh solution of aqueous KOH (B. D. H., 'AR' grade) was always used. Elico-pH meter, in conjunction with hydrogen glass electrode and S. C. E. was used for pH measurements. Standard solution of potassium

hydroxide was added to the reagent vessel from a microburette (least count 0.05 ml). All the pH measurements were performed at 29 ± 0.1 using Toshniwal model thermostat

Results and Discussion

Bjerrum's method has certain limitations when applied to aqueous-mixed alcoholic medium with more than 50 per cent alcohol, since the pH-scale set for aqueous medium is not applicable to non-aqueous medium. The values of stability constant determined for these systems would not, therefore, be the real values but would be the apparent ones. But here, since the studies were carried out in alcohol-water mixtures with more than 50 per cent water, the stability constants determined may be taken as real values.

The pK value (8.1) of BTSC determined pH-metrically, was in close agreement with the value obtained by polarographic method⁶. pH-metric titrations performed with mixtures of metal-ligand, ligand and metal separately against 0.1 M KOH showed lowering of pH, proving liberation of H^+ ions as a result of complex formation. Maximum lowering of pH in the case of 1 : 2 Cu -BTSC mixture and the inflection corresponding to 2 moles of KOH : 1 mole of copper acetate indicated 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in the complex.

pH-metric titration of BTSC alone and in the presence of different concentration of Cu^{2+} ions performed according to the method recommended by Calvin and Melchoir⁷, gave typical pH-metric curves when titrated against standard KOH . From these curve at various values of pH, a set of $\bar{n}$ values was determined and the concentration of free ligand ($\bar{A}$) was calculated. The values of $\bar{n}$ were plotted against the corresponding values of pA or $-\log(A)$. As a first approximation the value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and at $\bar{n}=1.5$ are equal to $\log K_1$ (3.703) and $\log K_2$ (3.037) respectively. The overall stability constant ($\log K$) came to be 6.740.

These temporary constants were corrected by Bjerrum's method⁸ of successive approximation. The value of spreading factor 'x' was found to be 1.0765 and the corrected values of formation function ($\bar{n}$) for each corresponding value of ($\bar{A}$) were then plotted against $-\log(A)$. The final values of $\log K_1 = 3.85$, $\log K_2 = 2.90$ and overall $\log K = 6.75$ were obtained.

From the results it is clear that $\bar{n}$ increases with the increase in pH showing thereby that it is the anionic form which takes part in the reaction.

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A Dynamic TG Study of *Bis*(acetylacetonato)-Copper(II)

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THE thermal decomposition of *bis*(acetylacetonato)-copper(II), [Cu(acac)₂], has been studied by dynamic thermogravimetry. The compound has been reported to be stable and non-volatile¹ upto 191° and to decompose at higher temperatures in the absence of air to acac and metallic copper². In the present investigation carried out in static air, the residue left behind has been shown to be CuO by analysis. In this dynamic TG study, the fractional decomposition values (αs) were employed in studying the kinetics of the overall decomposition process by methods described elsewhere^{3,4,5}. Different functional forms of α, viz f(α)s, assumed to govern the rate controlling process, were chosen for obtaining

the g(α) values (where $g(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)}$) from rate law

$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k f(\alpha)$. These g(α) values were used to evaluate

the kinetic parameters

Dynamic TG traces of the pure and dry complex (125 mg; mesh 200-240) prepared by known methods⁶ were obtained using 'Stanton' recording thermobalance (Model TR-1). The heating rate was 4° min⁻¹.

The TG trace redrawn as mass of sample versus temperature and the DTG curve are given in Fig. 1. The temperature of inception, T_i, temperature of completion, T_c, and peak temperature of decomposition, T_p, are 463, 538 and 524°K respectively. Mass loss found for the decomposition (95 mg) at T_c was in excellent agreement with the theoretical requirement (94.6 mg). Plots were made, g(α) versus temperature, for different mechanistic models for the decomposition and are set out in Fig. 2. From the linear portion of such plots, (i.e. 5, 6 and 7 in the figure) the frequency factor, Z, activation energy E* and entropy of activation ΔS* were

Fig. 1. TG, DTG curves

○-TG, ●-DTG

Fig. 2. Mechanistic plots

$g(\alpha)$: $\Delta \alpha^2$, $\Delta \alpha + (1-\alpha) \ln(1-\alpha)$,
 $\square [1-(1-\alpha)^{1/2}]^2$, $\square [1-\frac{2}{3}\alpha] - (1-\alpha)^{3/2}$,
 $\circ -\ln(1-\alpha)$, $\bullet [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$,
 $\ominus [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/3}$, $\bullet 1-(1-\alpha)^{1/2}$, $\circ 1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}$

calculated by methods described elsewhere^{4,7} and are presented in Table 1. Although three model

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS

Form of f(α)	g(α)	Frequency factor Z	Energy of activation, E* (k. J. mole ⁻¹)
(1-α)	-ln(1-α)	7.9 × 10 ¹⁰	184.8
2(1-α) [-ln(1-α)] ^{1/2}	[-ln(1-α)] ^{1/2}	5.6 × 10 ⁸	64.9
3(1-α) [-ln(1-α)] ^{1/3}	-ln(1-α)] ^{1/3}	2.6 × 10 ⁷	41.4